

Case No: 01 Male
Date 02 Female
Time 03 Other
Times retweeted 04 Unidentified

Suspended account?

01 Yes
02 No

Religion

01 Christian
02 Muslim
03 Hindu
04 Sikh

Deleted/unavailable tweet?

01 Yes
02 No

05 Buddhist
06 Jewish
07 Other

Tweet type

01 Original tweet
02 Retweet
03 Quote tweet
04 Reply

08 Atheist
99 Unidentified

Position on Muslims/Islam

[If Quote tweet] **Response to original tweet**

01 Agreement/endorsement
02 Disagreement
03 Mixed/qualification

01 Anti-Muslim
02 Supports Muslims
03 Mixed
04 Neutral/no view

04 Other
99 N/A

Position on Brexit

01 Anti-Brexit
02 Pro-Brexit
03 Mixed
04 Neutral/no view

Gender

Affiliation

01 Individual

02 State Institution/ Politician

03 Leftist or Social justice advocacy groups

04 Alt right group

05 Mainstream media organisation / journalist

06 Blogger/ alternative media organisation /
journalist

07 Independent political
analyst/commentator/author

08 NGO

09 Celebrity

10 Parody account

11 Academic

12 Mixed

13 Pressure group

14 Charity

98 Other

99 Unidentified

Location

01 UK

02 US/ North America

03 Europe

04 South Asia (India, Pakistan, Bangladesh)

05 Other Asian countries

06 MENA region

07 Other African countries

08 Australasia/Oceania

09 South/Central America

10 Russia

11 Mixed (two or more locations are
mentioned)

12 Other

99 None mentioned

Primary Topic

Secondary Topic

01 Anti-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [negative trait]')

02 Anti-Muslim, specific (extremism, evil, radicalisation, anti-Quran, anti-Islamic scripture etc)

03 Terrorism

04 Islamification/ spread of Islam (Cultural clash, censorship, Islam taking over the world, conversion, attacks on 'our' culture, country, Shariah law, references to the movement of refugees, Muslim problem, cultural deviance)

05 Scapegoating Muslims for Brexit

11 Pro-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [positive trait]')

12 Pro-Muslim, specific (contribution to society, acts of kindness, religion of peace, scientific endeavours etc)

13 Muslims are victims/ discrimination/racism/ Islamophobia

14 Brexit and anti-Muslim politics (eg blame politicians, globalisation, economics, social structures etc)

15 Racism in British politics

16 Racism in US politics

21 Politics, general

22 Pro Conservative/right agendas

23 Anti Conservative/right agendas

24 Pro Labour/ left agendas

25 Anti Labour/ left agendas / anti 'woke'

26 Pro-far right agenda

27 Anti far right agenda

28 Pro white supremacy

29 Anti white supremacy

30 Immigration

31 Community relations/cohesion

32 Relating Brexit to Indian politics

33 Relating Brexit to US politics

34 Pro LibDem

35 Anti LibDem

41 Left-wing criticism of mainstream media

42 Right-wing criticism of mainstream media

43 Tweet disseminates/premised on conspiracy theory

44 Tweet identifies/alleges conspiracy theory

45 antisemitism

99 Other

Hashtags – only coding content of tweet

Hashtag 1

Hashtag 2

Hashtag 3

- 1 antisemitism
- 2 bagdad
- 3 bbc
- 4 bbcdebate
- 5 bbcleadersdebate
- 6 borisjohnson
- 7 brexit
- 8 brexitday
- 9 brexitparty
- 10 britain
- 11 corbyn
- 12 crimes
- 13 danger
- 14 dehors
- 15 eu
- 16 ge2019
- 17 generalelection2019
- 18 happybrexitday
- 19 hidalgo
- 20 islam
- 21 islamogauchos
- 22 islamophobia
- 23 jeremycorbyn
- 24 jeremyvine
- 25 johnson
- 26 leadersdebate
- 27 lies
- 28 london
- 29 londonbridgeattack
- 30 macron
- 31 mexico
- 32 muslim
- 33 muslims
- 34 nevercorbyn
- 35 nexit
- 36 nhs
- 37 notmygovernment

- 38 paris
- 39 politicslive
- 40 pologne
- 41 racism
- 42 sadiqkhan
- 43 salopard
- 44 scrapthelicencefee
- 45 tories
- 46 trump
- 47 uk
- 48 ukelection
- 49 votefaiza
- 50 votelabour
- 51 Other
- 52 None

URL? [in original content]

01 Yes

02 No

Image(s)? [in original content]

01 Yes

02 No

Icons/Emojis? [in original content]

01 Yes

02 No

URL? [in QT content]

01 Yes

02 No

03 N/A

04 Unknown

Image(s)? [in QT content]

01 Yes

02 No

03 N/A

04 Unknown

Icons/Emojis? [in QT content]

01 Yes

02 No

03 N/A

04 Unknown